

 FINISH	 CHALLENGE	 BONUS (3 points)	 GO BACK	 MAXI BONUS 10 POINTS	CHALLENGE
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 CHALLENGE	 GO TO START	 MOVE UP TO 5 CELLS	 CHALLENGE	 HOSPITAL	TRANSIT PASS (3 points)	TRANSIT PASS (3 points)
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 GO TO ANY CELL NEXT TURN	 LOCAL MARKET	 CHALLENGE	 DIGITAL PLATFORM	 CHALLENGE	TRANSIT	 BONUS (3 points)
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 PENALTY (pay 5 points)	 DATA BREACH	 MUNICIPALITY	 GYM	 REVERSE DIRECTION	 ROLL AGAIN	 CHALLENGE	TRANSIT PASS (3 points)	TRANSIT PASS (3 points)
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 COURT	 PENALTY (pay 5 points)	 DATA BREACH	 CHALLENGE	 BANK
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 PERSONAL DATA INFRINGEMENT PENALTY (pay 10 points)	 POST OFFICE	 BONUS (3 points)	 TELECOM PROVIDER	 CHALLENGE	 PHARMACY	 CLOTHING STORE	 CHALLENGE	 STREAMING SERVICE	 COFFEE SHOP
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 PENALTY (pay 5 points)	 POLICE STATION	 UNIVERSITY	 CHALLENGE	 REPORT AN ISSUE
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 DATA BREACH	 POLICE STATION	 UNIVERSITY	 CHALLENGE	 REPORT AN ISSUE
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 PENALTY (pay 5 points)	 DATA BREACH	 REVERSE DIRECTION	 SOCIAL NETWORKS	 CHALLENGE	 LIBRARY
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 PENALTY (pay 5 points)	 REVERSE DIRECTION	 SOCIAL NETWORKS	 CHALLENGE	 LIBRARY
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CHALLENGES

BONUSES

PENALTIES

